

EFFECTS OF FDI ON ORGANISED RETAILERS IN INDIA: AN EVIDENCE FROM WAL-MART

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INTRODUCTION

Foreign direct investment (FDI) in the retail sector in India was limited. On September 14, 2012, government eased retail policy for the second time by allowing Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) in the Multi-brand Retail Sector (MBRT) up to 51% with some conditions and up to 100% FDI in single brand retail trading with Government approval. Earlier in 2006, the government eased retail policy for the first time, allowing up to 51 per cent FDI through the single brand retail route.

While it is not easy to be successful in a place where culture, tradition and food habits change every 124 miles still foreign retailers will bring technology, efficiency in supply chain management and global experiences from previous ventures. They will effectively harness their expertise with cold storage technologies to lure customers with fresh and exotic vegetables, fruits and organic produce. Organized retail sector is already facing the competition from unorganized sector, also with allowing investment by foreign retailers in multi-brand retailing may lead to unfair competition and ultimately result in large-scale exit of incumbent domestic retailers. It has been observed that the organized retail sector in India is an infant industry. It is too young to compete with foreign retailers like Wal-Mart on the level of warehousing technology and efficiency in supply chain management.

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INDIAN RETAIL INDUSTRY: GROWTH AND TRANSFORMATION

The retailing sector in India has undergone a significant transformation. Indian Retail Industry was placed the 5th largest retail destination and the second most attractive market for investment in the globe after Vietnam as reported by AT Kearney's seventh annual Globe Retail Development Index (GRDI), in 2008. Before 1980, Indian retail continued in the form of kiranas, the unorganized retailing. Retail outlets like Food World, Nilgiris came into existence in the later part of the 1990s. In 1997, FDI in cash and carry (wholesale) with 100% ownership was allowed under the Government approval route. It was brought under the automatic route in 2006. Bharti Enterprises and Wal-Mart entered into a joint venture in August 2007 and started cash-and-carry stores named 'Best Price Modern Wholesale' in 2009 while Britain's Tesco formed a tie-up with the giant Tata Group conglomerate. Currently big players like Reliance, Tata's, Bharti, ITC, Big Bazaar, Shoppers' stop, Vishal Mega Mart and other reputed companies have entered into organized retail business. Allowing 51% FDI in single brand retail in 2006, led to direct entrance of the multinational companies like Nike, Reebok, Metro etc. or through joint ventures like Wal-Mart with Bharti, Tata with Tesco etc.

Retailing in India accounts for 14 to 15% of its GDP. India is one of the fastest growing retail markets in the world, with 1.2 billion people. In 2010, larger format convenience stores and supermarkets accounted for about 4% of the industry in 2010, and these large format stores were present only in large urban centers. In September, 2012, government announced retail reforms for both multi-brand stores (51% FDI with condition) and single-brand stores (100% FDI with Government approval). These market reforms paved the way for retail innovation and competition with multi-brand retailers such as Wal-Mart, Carrefour and Tesco, as well as single brand majors such as IKEA, Nike, and Apple.

FDI Policy with Regard to Retailing in India: Single Brand Retailing

EARLIER	NOW
<p>For Single Brand Retail Trading (SBRT) sector – only 51% FDI permitted – subject to approvals and conditions such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Products should be of a “Single Brand” only. ➤ Products to be under the same brand in one or more countries if are sold outside India. ➤ “Single Brand” products should be branded during manufacturing ➤ The foreign investor should be the owner of the brand 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ FDI in single brand retail trading is permitted up to 100% with Government approval. ➤ Products to be sold should be of a “Single Brand” only. ➤ 30% sourcing is to be done from micro and small industries (investment in Plant and Machinery not exceeding US \$ 1mm). ➤ This condition will ensure that SME sector, including artisans, craftsman, handicraft and cottage industry gets the benefits of liberalization

The Policy: Multi Brand Retailing

EARLIER: FDI in Multi Brand Retail Trading was not allowed.

NOW: FDI in Multi Brand Retail Trade is permitted up to 51%, subject to following conditions:

- Outlets to be set up - only in cities with a population of more than 1m (within a 10km range).
- Minimum investment by the foreign investor -US \$100mm and at least 30% of the procurement of manufactured/ processed products shall be sourced from “small industries” (investment in Plant and Machinery not exceeding US \$1million).
- Sourcing requirements will be checked together for first five years – after that on a annual basis.
- Retail trading by means of e-commerce – not permissible.

CURRENT CONSTRAINTS

The Indian retail sector, particularly organized retail, is still under-developed and in a nascent stage. Organized retail sector is already facing the competition from unorganized sector. The tax structure in India also favors small retail business. Organized retail sector has to pay huge taxes, which is negligible for small retail business. Thus, the cost of business operations is very high in India. Companies like Wal-Mart that grew from the ground-up leveraged the infrastructure of U.S.A to build a large supply-chain which has been the backbone of its success. The story in India is very different. Inadequate highways, the absence of cold storage facilities, an underdeveloped supply chain, lack of trained work force and low skill level for retailing management further makes the sector quite complex.

While India is the second largest producer of fruits and vegetables (about 180 million MT), it has a very limited integrated cold-chain infrastructure, with only 5386 stand-alone cold storages, having a total capacity of 23.6 million MT. , 80% of this is used only for potatoes. The chain is highly fragmented. As a result, it is difficult to link perishable horticultural commodities to distant markets, including overseas markets, round the year. Farmers have to face heavy losses in terms of wastage in quality and quantity of produce due to lack of adequate storage facilities.

India is the seventh largest country (land mass: 3.2 million sq. kms.) with varying climatic conditions over the country. Taste and preferences of people vary strongly all across the country. Catering to people in 35 states and union territories is equivalent to catering to people in 35 countries, leading to complexities in merchandise / inventory management. Infrastructure has been developing at a rapid pace over the past decade but has still a significant ground to cover.

Globally, retailers maintain a direct relationship with their suppliers. Due to the complex taxation structure and geographic spread of the country, most FMCG companies have developed regional distribution and re-distribution network. Cutting out the distribution network will hurt operating structures of distributors, who had opposed FMCG companies selling directly to retailers considering themselves as an industry body. Rent forms a large portion of the total expenditure (6 to 11 percent of the revenue) in retailer's income statement and can more often than not convert a profitable store into loss making. The challenge for a retailer would be to find the right location for their stores either in malls or as a standalone store to be able to generate enough footfalls.

The Indian consumers' buying habits have still not changed, where people prefer to buy most of the fruits and vegetables on a daily basis. The Indian consumers have a strong preference for freshly cooked food over packaged food mainly attributed to dietary patterns, poor electricity supply, low penetration of refrigerators and a family structure where one of the primary roles of the housewife is feeding the family. There is also an impact on the basket size because of non-availability of personal transport facilities, due to which the consumers prefer to buy smaller quantities from stores conveniently located near their homes.

THE EVIDENCE FROM WAL-MART

Wal-Mart discount store was first established in a small town Rogers in Arkansas by Sam Walton in July, 1962. Since its founding, Wal-Mart has completely revolutionized the retail industry. Its emphasis on low prices and efficiency has spread throughout the industry, spawning a surge in price competition and consolidation among food retailers. Wal-Mart international operations contribute about 40% to the company's value. Wal-Mart had 5,650 international stores in 2011 and It is forecasted this figure to grow to 6,280 by the end of 2014.

From the beginning Wal-Mart focused on increasing the volume of customers' visits to realize economies of scale. By keeping prices low, it increased sales so much more than just to compensate for the decrease in markup. When Wal-Mart enters a market, prices decrease by 8 percent in rural areas and 5 in urban areas. For example, when Wal-Mart entered the grocery business the prices fell by fifteen percent. This unrelenting drive to keep prices low puts pressure on all the stakeholders: workers, managers and suppliers. Wal-Mart competes with establishment in a wide array of sectors both directly and indirectly.

Wal-Mart derived competitive advantage through adoption of highly efficient logistics and distribution system by leveraging new technologies. It adopted vertically integrated distribution system. It was one of the first retailers to adopt electronic scanners at the registers which were tied to an inventory control system such that it could know immediately which items were selling well. Wal-Mart procures goods directly from manufacturers bypassing all intermediaries and always drives hard bargain from suppliers. It spends a significant amount of time meeting vendors and understanding their cost structure. Once satisfied, it establishes long term

relationship with vendors. It is in constant touch with suppliers through computer network. The long term relationship of repeated interactions reduces transaction costs of exchange. Once goods procured, its warehouses supply 85 percent of the inventory as compared to 50-60 percent for competitors. Consequently, it is able to provide replenishments within two days against at least five days for competitors and shipping costs on average turn out to be 3 percent as against 5 percent for competitors.

Fishman (2006) examines “The Wal-Mart effect is the suburbanization of shopping; the downward pressure on wages at all kinds of stores trying to compete with Wal-Mart; the consolidation of consumer product companies trying to compete with Wal-Mart’s scale;..... In the same decade that Wal-Mart has come to dominate the grocery business in the United States, 31 supermarket chains have sought bankruptcy protection; 27 of these chains cite competition from Wal-Mart as a factor. That too is the Wal-Mart effect.”

Recent history proves that when large international retailers enter, informal and small-scale businesses are forced to shut their doors. A United States Census Bureau study of the US retail sector between 1976 and 2005, found that “the entry and growth of Big-Box stores (hypermarkets) has a substantial negative impact on employment growth and survival of single unit and smaller chain stores that operate in the same detailed industry as the Big-Box... the impact is largest if the single unit or smaller chain store is within 1 mile or 1 to 5 miles of the Big-Box store relative to being 5 to 10 miles from the Big-Box.

The negative effects of large retailers on small retailers are not restricted to the United States. A 2010 paper authored by Thabelo Rabhugoni and M.fundo Ngobese of the Competition Commission of South Africa suggests that “larger discounts negotiated by larger buyers have a consequence for discounts negotiated by smaller buyers.” According to the analysis, South Africa’s retail sector has become more formalized and concentrated as a result small retailers have exited the market.

Thailand is frequently referred to as a country in which FDI had an adverse effect on the local retailers. It permits 100% foreign equity, with no limit on the number of outlets. Entry of foreign

players in a recessionary economy adversely impacted all segments – wholesalers, manufacturers and domestic retailers in the short run. Many local players had to close down their business.

In the case of Mexico and other Latin American countries which are geographically close to the U.S., Wal-Mart has been successful. Wal-Mart entered Mexico in 1991 with a joint venture with the largest Mexican firm Aurrera. And in 1997, Wal-Mart bought Aurrera. Wal-Mart modernized warehousing, distribution and inventory management which reduced costs and prices significantly.

Wal-Mart entered China in 1996 and now it operates 352 stores in 130 cities. Wal-Mart has been able to cater to the rapidly growing Chinese market at around 18 percent annually. About 20,000 Chinese suppliers provide Wal-Mart with 70 percent of its global sales. Thirty percent of Chinese exports are accounted by Wal-Mart.

There has also been much speculation about the competitive effects of Wal-Mart's expansion; for example, the February 2005 bankruptcy filing of Winn-Dixie, a large supermarket chain based in Florida, was widely blamed on Wal-Mart's rise. In fact, the vast majority of supermarket bankruptcy cases in the last decade have cited Wal-Mart as a catalyst

QUESTIONS

1. Attempt a Porter's 5-Forces strategy analysis for the Indian retail industry.
2. Diagnose the possible effects of global players like Wal-Mart on domestic firms in India.
3. Identify the major areas of focus and priority for domestic retailers in short term.
4. Suggest the strategies to be adopted by domestic retailers to preempt foreign firms in long term.

TEACHING NOTES

OVERVIEW

Organised retailing in India with less than 5% share of today's market is already facing the competition from unorganized retailers and many new giant foreign retailers are about to enter in near future. Whereas foreign retailers are ready to make use of their expertise in supply chain management and cold storage technologies to lure customers with fresh and exotic vegetables,

fruits and organic produce. But Indian Organised retailers have their own constraints of being under-developed and in a nascent stage. The foreign retailers in general are very efficient and utilise all their resources effectively and infrastructure in particular large supply-chain which has been the backbone of their success. The story in India is very different. Inadequate highways, the absence of cold storage facilities, an underdeveloped supply chain, lack of trained work force and low skill level for retailing management further makes the sector quite complex.

The present case shows how foreign retailers may affect organised retailers in India on the ground of certain factors such as warehousing technology, Supply Chain management, and price of the merchandise. It is a case for identifying the major areas of focus and priority and for devising the strategy for organised retailers to preempt foreign firms in long term. Although, the strategic management field has developed and grown in many different directions, most standard textbooks continue to use the SWOT model as their centerpiece. Likewise, despite the rate at which they introduce new techniques, many strategy consultants continue to rely on SWOT model and other design school notions. SWOT model analysis is a proper tool for devising the strategy in the given case.

APPLICATION

The case study is best suited for management students who have some basic understanding of different concepts of strategy formulation and strategic analysis. The case can also be discussed among the participants of a management training programme which is focused on the strategy formation. If the participants have some experience in use of strategic models they can add value of their daily working to the discussion and in arriving to some solutions for the problems given in the present case.

OBJECTIVES OF THE CASE

The case is typically a complex case in which most of the facts have been stated, however, the reader is at liberty to assume few of the unstated facts. A few of the data has also been given which may or may not be relevant to the discussion of the case. It is readers' discretion of using the given data. The main objective is to diagnose the possible effects of global players like Wal-Mart on organised retailers in India.

The other objectives of the case are to attempt the competitive analysis of organised retailing in India. It also includes the development of strategy for organized retailers in India to compete with foreign retailers who will be operating in India as FDI. The case introduces the concept of internal and external appraisal of the industry to arrive on a suitable strategy.

TEACHING SUGGESTIONS

Competitive analysis

The internal factors may be viewed as strengths or weaknesses depending upon their impact on the organization's objectives. The internal factors may include all of the 4Ps; as well as personnel, finance, manufacturing capabilities, and so on. The external factors may include macroeconomic matters, technological change, legislation, and socio-cultural changes, as well as changes in the marketplace or competitive position. The strategy is created by combining the distinctive competencies with the key success factors which needs to be addressed by the organization. Two other factors believed important in strategy making managerial values and social responsibility are perceived by its managers. Managerial values are the beliefs and preferences of those who formally lead the organization. Social responsibility is an ethical ideology or theory that an entity, be it an organization or individual, has an obligation to act to benefit society at large. It is a duty every individual or organization has to perform so as to maintain a balance between the economy and the ecosystem.

The internal appraisal system provides the strengths and weaknesses of organization and external appraisal system provides with the threats and opportunities present in the environment. At one hand strengths and weaknesses gives the distinctive competencies of the organization whereas, threats and opportunities identify the key success factors of that organization. The strategy is **created by combining the distinctive competencies with the key success** factors. Two other factors believed important in strategy making managerial values and social responsibility are perceived by its managers. Managerial values are the beliefs and preferences of those who formally lead the organization. Social responsibilities are specifically the ethics of the society in which the organization functions.

Once alternative strategies have been determined, next step in the model is to evaluate them and choose the best one. The assumption, in other words, is that several strategies have been designed and are to be evaluated so that one of them can be selected. Rumelt (1997) has provided the framework for making evaluation in terms of a series of tests:

Consistency: The strategy must not present mutually inconsistent goals and policies.

Consonance: The strategy must represent an adaptive response to the external environment and to the critical changes occurring within it.

Advantage: The strategy must provide for the creation and/or maintenance of a competitive advantage in the selected area of activity.

Feasibility: The strategy must neither overtax available resources nor create unsolvable sub-problems.

Once a strategy has been agreed upon, it is then implemented. The design school advocates that after the appraisals have been completed to narrow down to convergent choice, the process diverges again to ensure the implementation across the entire organization.

The class of students or the participants of the training program may be divided into small groups to discuss the case among themselves. The students with different length of experience will be differently able to contribute in arriving to the solutions of the problem.

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